

RISING FROM THE AFTERMATH: A QUALITATIVE STUDY OF COVID-19 SURVIVORS

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Rising from the Aftermath: A Qualitative Study of COVID-19 Survivors

Danica V. Delima*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study is a collection of lessons learned from people who have personally dealt with COVID-19, particularly the so-called mild-to-moderate cases that resolved themselves when they were left alone. Experiences of people following a clinical COVID-19 diagnosis and self-care treatments is closely tied to Self-Care Nursing Theory which focuses on a person's capacity for self-care. Qualitative methodology is utilized to understand the irrational sensations, conceptions, and beliefs of the Covid-19 survivors. Striving to completely appreciate the phenomenon by discussing the individuals' lived experiences. Questionnaire-guided interview study of 10 people aged 18 and up who lived in Tarlac City and had positive COVID-19 or antibody tests were chosen using purposive sampling. People more likely to get COVID-19 from members of their own home or family, according to the study. The respondents also recounted a wide spectrum of symptoms that they encountered during their sickness. Most study participants believed that recovery time was longer than the commonly accepted two-week period, which is a significant finding. According to the findings of this study, a four-week recuperation period is normally required. 60% of participants reported being subjected to COVID-19 stigma, such as avoidance by others after they had recovered and downplaying of their sickness or COVID-19 experience by others. Individuals then recounted their COVID-19 experiences to inform and motivate the public, particularly those who have not yet infected the coronavirus. According to the findings of this study, the road to rehabilitation for self-care patients in isolation may be challenging and slow for certain people. As a result, it is recommended that a policy be established to promote and encourage the establishment of an intervention program that supports and encourages holistic rehabilitation and will take care of the patients' physical and psychological well-being as they advance through the self-care phase of their recovery.

Keywords: *COVID-19 survivors, mild-to-moderate cases, experiences*

Introduction

The novel coronavirus (COVID-19) is a pandemic public health crisis rapidly threatening the world. Deeper understandings of these lifetime experiences delve deeper into the experiences of individuals with direct knowledge of COVID-19, notably the so-called mild-to-moderate cases that resolved while in isolation.

As of October 22, 2020, there have been over 41.1 million confirmed cases and 1.1 million deaths worldwide due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Months into the pandemic, many unknowns exist about the novel coronavirus, its transmission, and infected individuals' experiences. It is a fact that the severity of COVID-19 can vary from mild to severe. The CDC and China's studies suggest that according to WHO, 80% of COVID-19 cases exhibit mild to moderate symptoms.

Patients with mild-to-moderate COVID-19 are advised to self-isolate due to limited healthcare capacity. Innumerable of these patients, especially during the initial phases of the outbreak (February and March 2020 in the Philippines), received little to no clinical care; consequently, there is a crucial knowledge gap regarding their experiences with COVID-19. The DOH and IATF-EID stressed the importance of identifying factors that caused the virus to spread early. Doing so will aid in future decision-making and strengthen measures to predict possible transmission revivals. (Rosario, 2020)

In contrast to admitted hospital patients, the number of individuals with mild-to-moderate COVID-19 symptoms remained relatively understudied and encompassed the "undocumented masses"; nevertheless, this population contributes significantly to the virus's rapid transmission. The study aims to provide insights from COVID-19 survivors whose experiences are not documented in medical records. This study aims to spread awareness about how people in the Philippines contracted the coronavirus, the range of symptoms they experienced, the duration of their infection, and their experiences on the road to recovery through individual experiences. Given the current resurgence in the Philippines, such knowledge can inform guidelines for most instances of COVID-19 considered to be of mild to moderate severity. In this research, it is optimal to develop and deploy a web-based platform for gathering data from participants who have recovered from COVID-19 or are on the road to recovery (World Health Organization 2020).

The main goal of this study is to gather insights from people who have experienced COVID-19, especially those with mild-to-moderate symptoms that lack detailed descriptions in the literature. The researcher will recruit ten individuals from 76 barangays in Tarlac City with laboratory-confirmed positive COVID-19 tests and those identified as presumptively positive by clinical staff to share their experience with COVID-19.

The researcher anticipates that this study will result in an intervention program that supports the rehabilitation of COVID-19 patients in physical, psychological, and social aspects.

According to a similar study, COVID-19 diagnosis and hospitalization are disproportionately more significant among disadvantaged

individuals. The study examined the lived experience of people diagnosed with COVID-19. Through semi-structured interviews with individuals diagnosed with COVID-19, the study identified three themes: panic amidst a COVID-19 diagnosis, repercussions of the diagnosis, and personal assessment of risks within one's environment.

Patients from Sainfer's study indicated that fear of death, limited health benefits, financial challenges, and fears of infecting loved ones with the virus were significant concerns. Most COVID-19 patients viewed God as their only hope for survival. However, none of the patients reported receiving spiritual guidance from medical professionals. It is the first study to examine the lived experience of black people diagnosed with COVID-19. Our findings indicate several risks that place this population at an increased risk for COVID-19 and the areas where further initiatives are required to address these deficiencies. It could enhance patient care by integrating public health activities to reduce socioeconomic impediments and spirituality into clinical care.

Another related study in Palestine exploring the lived experiences of cured COVID-19 patients may have scientific, social, and policy repercussions for the healthcare system. This multicenter descriptive phenomenological study was conducted to investigate the lived experiences of Palestinian COVID-19 survivors. This study used descriptive phenomenology. The researcher drew the study students using a method of purposive sampling. Twenty patients who recovered from COVID-19 underwent interviews qualitatively using a semi-structured format.

The interviews were transcribed using Colaizzi's phenomenological approach, which involved the following steps:

- Familiarization
- Identification of significant statements
- Formulation of the meanings
- Clustering of the themes
- Construction of a comprehensive description of the phenomenon
- Production of the fundamental structure
- Verification of the actual structure

In the study from Palestine, fourteen male and six female COVID-19 survivors participated in semi-structured interviews. The duration of the discussion was 998 minutes in total (16.6 hours). The qualitative data obtained during the interviews found five significant themes and sixteen sub-themes that exhaustively represented the phenomenon. The main articles were relevant to emotions after learning about the infection, experiencing social exclusion and stigma, experiencing symptoms, supportive treatments, herbs, rituals, and social support, and life after recovery.

Due to their infection, the interviewees endured negative emotions, social marginalization, and stigma. Promoting mental health may need to be incorporated into the care plan for COVID-19 patients. More research is required to determine whether adding mental health professionals to the care team of COVID-19 patients can improve their experiences (Alkaissi, 2022).

Another similar study concerning the lived experiences of COVID-19 survivors Qualitative research provided a comprehensive insight and description of COVID-19 patients' disease experiences. Sixteen patients who received COVID-19 treatment in isolation were interviewed using in-depth interviews until data saturation, with the interviews recorded and transcribed verbatim. The data underwent evaluation using the phenomenological method of Colaizzi. After being tested in a laboratory, the isolated individuals confirmed their COVID-19 diagnosis. Their treatment was marked by uncertainty and desperation.

The participants were shocked and dissatisfied by the extreme violation of their privacy during the quarantine procedure and system. Participants in COVID-19 cases experienced social stigma, guilt, negative attitudes, and adverse effects from social media. Symptoms also caused mental and physical challenges. Despite this, they rediscovered meaningful relationships with the help of their family and friends. Concerned professionals must provide COVID-19 patients with an integrated psychosocial rehabilitation program to eliminate social stigma and enhance their resilience (Son et al., 2021).

Research Questions

The study sought input from people who had directly dealt with COVID-19, especially those who had self-resolved while isolating with mild-to-moderate symptoms. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following:

1. What is the demographic information of people who dealt with COVID-19, particularly those with mild-to-moderate cases that resolved on their own while isolated?
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. civil status;
 - 1.4. barangay of residence;
 - 1.5. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.6. employment status;
 - 1.7. field of occupation;

- 1.8. household size;
- 1.9. role in the family;
- 1.10. covid-19 testing received;
- 1.11. preexisting medical condition?
2. What do COVID-19 survivors with mild-to-moderate symptoms who self-resolved in isolation say about their experience?
 - 1.1. Onset, testing, and contraction of COVID-19;
 - 1.2. Deeper look at COVID-19 symptoms;
 - 1.3. Recovery from COVID-19?
3. What are the lessons learned of COVID-19 survivors from their experiences?
4. What intervention program could be developed that promotes and supports comprehensive recovery (i.e., physical, psychological, and social) among COVID-19 patients?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized qualitative research to understand the subjective experiences, beliefs, and concepts of the COVID-19 survivors. It aims to deeply understand the phenomenon or event by describing the participants' lived experiences. Specifically, the study utilized a phenomenological research design. The qualitative approach is considered appropriate because it involves the use of methods of data collection that include a comprehensive understanding of a phenomenon and seek to produce information based on human experience (Sandelowski, 2004). On the other hand, a researcher can also examine the perspectives and perceptions of many individuals (Patton, 2003), which leads to our systematic and detailed interpretation of the phenomenon under investigation (Bryman, 2012; Patton, 2003).

Phenomenology is a branch of qualitative research that explores the shared characteristics of a group's lived experiences. Phenomenology is a branch of qualitative research exploring shared aspects of a group's lived experiences. The approach's primary objective is to arrive at a description of the nature of the observed occurrence (Creswell, 2013). Thematic analysis is employed by putting the content of the data in focus and involves coding and organizing the data to identify critical themes (Bliss, 2016).

Participants

The questionnaire-guided interview study used purposive sampling to recruit ten adult participants aged 18 years or older who resided in Tarlac City and tested positive results for COVID-19 or antibodies. Participants were recruited using various methods, including online support groups for COVID-19 survivors, advertisements in local news outlets, and professional and other networks. The study measured participants' knowledge of virus contraction, symptoms, and recovery experiences (Fricker, 2016).

Instruments

The primary research instrument used in this study is a self-created interview guide. The researcher's adviser validated it, after which the participant used the focus in a personal dialogue. This study's survey questionnaires were informed by numerous sources, including the Department of Health's (DOH) coronavirus case report and COVID-19. The organization is responsible for managing emerging infectious diseases is called the Inter-Agency Task Force for the Management of Emerging Infectious Diseases (IATF-EID). Knowledge gaps are identified in the literature. The survey covered descriptive characteristics, virus transmission, symptoms, coping, and recovery.

Procedure

All participants interested in the study were invited to complete a pre-survey about COVID-19 to screen for the following eligibility criteria: 18 years of age or older, living in Tarlac City, and having tested positive for COVID-19 and COVID-19 antibodies. Participants who meet these eligibility requirements are then asked for an interview, during which they share their stories about COVID-19. The research used a thematic analysis approach in interpreting the data and organizing them into codes and themes.

Data Analysis

All information and data gathered are treated with confidentiality. In focusing on the content and data for the socio-demographic profile of the respondents, a sample mean, median, and statistical mode treatment are employed. Researcher utilized Colaizzi's phenomenological method to analyze the data. A deductive approach is also to be employed, which involves analyzing the qualitative data based on the structure predetermined by the researcher. The researcher used the questions as a guide for analyzing the data. The data analyzed are then used to aid in an in-depth analysis and understanding of the participants' lived experiences in surviving the COVID-19 virus (Edward, 2011).

Results and Discussion

The Socio-demographic Summary of Respondents

This qualitative study included participation from ten individuals, ranging in Age from 18 to 55 years old, hailing from ten different

barangays in Tarlac City. The participants in this study were three adults (aged 36–55), five middle-aged adults (aged 25–35), and four young adults (aged 18–25). Out of the ten participants in the study, six were female, and four were male, including a housewife, a health worker, a social worker, a church worker, a university professor, a police officer, and college students.

There were a total of ten subjects. Of these ten people, eight (or 80%) received a positive laboratory test or antibody test for COVID-19, while the remaining two (or 20%) were verified presumptively positive by clinical personnel. In addition, two participants (or 20% of all participants) had at least one preexisting medical condition, and eight people (or 80%) had no preexisting medical condition.

Among the preexisting conditions that were recorded, the ones that occurred most frequently were high blood pressure or hypertension. Table 1 provides specific information regarding several additional descriptors, including participants' most outstanding level of education, household income, and occupation.

Within the full interview, using the questionnaire as a guide, five to ten questions (Sections D and E) addressed topics related to the Onset, testing, and contraction of COVID- 19.

Table 1. *The characteristics of COVID-19 patients*

Characteristics	N=10	% (n=10)
Age		
18-24	1	10%
25-35	6	60%
36-55	3	30%
56 and above	0	0%
Gender		
Male	4	40%
Female	6	60%
Highest level of education		
Bachelor’s degree	9	90%
Master’s degree	1	10%
Doctorate degree	0	
Employment status		
Full-time	6	60%
Part-time	2	20%
Unemployed	2	20%
Occupation		
Nonessential work	1	10%
Essential worker (healthcare)	3	30%
Essential worker (non-healthcare)	4	40%
Unemployed	1	10%
Student	1	10%

Table 1. A comprehensive breakdown of the participants' personal information.

COVID-19 survivors experiences

Within the full interview using the questionnaire as guide, there were a total of five to ten questions (Section D and E) that addressed topics related to the onset, testing, and contraction of COVID-19.

The Onset, Testing, and Contraction of Covid-19

When most participants started experiencing symptoms, they worked from home (60%), whereas only four performed outside the home (40%). In addition, all the participants claimed that before the Onset of their symptoms, they had been taking the recommended preventative measures, such as wearing gloves and masks, keeping a social distance, frequently cleaning their hands, and washing their hands. Nevertheless, it is essential to remember that most individuals experienced the development of symptoms during the initial rapid spread of COVID-19. This is also when suggestions for personal protective practices start to emerge. In hindsight, participants could narrow down the source of how they might have gotten COVID- 19, as presented in Figure 1B. Seventy percent (70%) of these people provided credible sources. However, only thirty percent (30%) of these participants shared what they thought to be the specific origins of their infection. According to the data, the virus's transmission most frequently occurred within a household or a family. In addition, seven participants (70%) stated that at least one additional member of their family or home had contracted COVID-19. This study implies that even when sufficient steps are taken to decrease the danger, there is still a reasonable possibility that the coronavirus may spread among people sharing a living space.

On the other hand, there needs to be more focus on COVID-19 spreading inside families or households. The most common source of

virus transmission was the essential worker who became infected with the virus while performing their job. All seven individuals (70%) reported this in the study. Most of those who said more precise sources of their infection agreed that this vector of virus transmission was most likely responsible for their disease.

According to the obtained results, the participants reported other sources of virus transmission. These sources include social gatherings (reported by 1 out of 10 people, or 10%), workplaces with non-essential workers (reported by 1 out of 10, or 10%), and even grocery stores (reported by 1 out of 10 people, or 10%). See Figure 1C for an illustration.

The symptoms of feeling feverish, having an intense, persistent, and dry cough, having difficulty breathing, feeling cold and calm, and having pains and aches in the muscles, chest, and throughout the body were the most frequent among patients. Other physiological experiences shared by the COVID-19 survivors, mentioned less frequently, were a lack of appetite, sore throats and tonsillitis, headaches of varying degrees, disorientation, changes in voice, insomnia, and the inability to smell or taste.

Major Mentions

"A high fever and excruciating pains tormented every area of my body..." "I continued to cough... I feared that I may die alone."

"...It's as if rice sacks surround my lungs, so when I take a big breath, I feel pressure."

"When I had COVID-19, I felt incredibly feverish. My temperature was constantly high, and I couldn't shake off the feeling of being extremely hot."

"Breathing became a struggle for me. Even simple tasks like walking or talking would leave me gasping for air. It was scary and made me realize how important healthy lungs are."

"Despite feeling feverish, I also experienced moments of feeling cold and oddly calm. It was as if my body couldn't regulate its temperature properly."

"The muscle and body aches were excruciating. It felt like my entire body was sore, and even the slightest movement would trigger sharp pains."

"COVID-19 left me feeling disoriented at times. I would have difficulty concentrating, and my thoughts felt foggy and confused."

"Sleeping became a struggle for me. I would toss and turn all night, unable to find a comfortable position. Insomnia added to the overall exhaustion."

Minor Mentions

"I lost my voice. At times, I was incapable of making any sound. Sometimes, I sounded like a frog." "I was unable to sleep at all... This lasted two days..."

"During my battle with COVID-19, I completely lost my appetite. Food had no appeal to me, and even the thought of eating made me feel nauseous."

"One of the most bothersome symptoms for me was the sore throat and tonsillitis. Swallowing became painful, and my throat felt constantly irritated."

"Headaches were a constant companion during my illness. They varied in intensity, but there was always some level of pressure and discomfort in my head."

Table 2. *The Onset, Testing and Contraction of COVID-19*

Themes	Codes	Result
Onset, Testing and Contraction of COVID-19	People infected with Covid-19	According to the study, a total of ten participants reported experiencing the beginning of COVID- 19 symptoms. Seven of them reported the onset of symptoms after the easing of the Enhanced Community Quarantine (ECQ), while the remaining three experienced symptoms in the last quarter of 2020. It's worth noting that most participants started experiencing symptoms during the initial fast spread of COVID-19, when personal protective practices were just starting to emerge.
	COVID-19 symptoms experienced	The most frequent symptoms reported by the participants included feeling feverish, having an intense, persistent, and dry cough, difficulty breathing, feeling cold and calm, and experiencing pains and aches in the muscles, chest, and throughout the body. Other less frequently mentioned symptoms among COVID- 19 survivors included a lack of appetite, sore throats and tonsillitis, varying degrees of headaches, disorientation, changes in voice, insomnia, and the inability to smell or taste.

Preventive/Precautionary measures to stop COVID-19 contraction	All participants claimed that prior to the onset of their symptoms, they had been following the recommended preventive measures, such as wearing gloves and masks, maintaining social distance, frequently cleaning their hands, and washing their hands regularly. However, despite these precautions, they still contracted the virus. This suggests that even with sufficient preventive measures in place, there is still a reasonable possibility of COVID-19 transmission among individuals sharing a living space.
Settings and workplaces of virus transmission	The study revealed that when most participants started experiencing symptoms, they were working from home (60%), while only four individuals (40%) worked outside the home. The most common source of virus transmission reported by the participants was essential workers who became infected while performing their jobs. All seven individuals (70%) attributed their infection to this source. Additionally, other reported sources of virus transmission included social gatherings (10%), workplaces with non-essential workers (10%), and even grocery stores (10%).

Deeper Look at the Covid-19 Symptoms

Most participants in this study managed their symptoms at home and/or in isolation (80%) one participant was hospitalized and one is considered an outpatient because medical consultation was done online, and care is done at home and in isolation; these participants represent people with mild-to-moderate severity of COVID-19. This is in alignment with the estimates in the current literature that about 80% of the COVID-19 cases are mild to moderate as opposed to severe.

Participants were asked to identify all symptoms they experienced during their illness with COVID-19. Figure 2B shows the prevalence of the well-recognized COVID-19 symptoms reported in this study population (N=10), with the top-4 reported symptoms being fatigue (10/10, 100%), shortness of breath (5/10, 50%), decreased sense of smell or taste (6/10, 60%), and fever (10/10, 100%). These more common symptoms have also been identified in earlier studies, albeit with different percentages for frequency of occurrence in various populations.

The research investigated a few of how the participants' mental health was affected while they were healing from the new coronavirus (COVID-19). According to the recorded experiences, most of these participants had a poor experience with their mental health, whereas just a small number had a pleasant mental experience. One participant recalled her emotions of remorse and embarrassment at the notion of infecting those she had encountered. As word of their condition spread, some individuals recalled being retaliated against and treated brutally by those in their immediate environment. The major sub-themes surrounding the negative mental experiences were being scared, panicky, and having moments of paranoia; some recalled having shown anxiety and worry as they tried to recover; one of the participants recalled her guilt and embarrassment.

Some survivors reported that they had experienced the moment when they cried and shivered over thoughts of having contracted the virus; a few recounted nightmares and suicidal thoughts; while others bemoaned the fact that they had to suffer the psychological effect of lacking the usual interpersonal relationships; some expressed their overwhelming and painful memories during their accounts of the mental health consequences of the pandemic.

Major Mentions

"It was difficult to be alone on my birthday; I was physically and mentally isolated. Numerous negative thoughts entered my mind... My mental health also deteriorated."

"I felt guilty because of the potential hazards that my family would be exposed to, both from contracting the virus from me and from being stigmatized as a result of being associated with a confirmed case."

"I was unable to sleep as anxiousness filled the room..."

"Despair seized me as I feared dying without being able to cling to the hands of my family and friends."

"I had a poor experience with my mental health. I felt scared and panicky at times. I also had moments of paranoia, constantly worrying about my recovery."

"I had moments when I cried and shivered with fear, just thinking about having contracted the virus. I also experienced nightmares and even had suicidal thoughts."

"It was overwhelming and painful. Not being able to have regular contact with loved ones took a toll on my mental well-being."

Minor Mentions

"I was terrified... and I'd never seen so many doctors wearing protective clothing before..."

"I was subjected to criticism and unpleasant remarks from the public and those who know me."

"I felt a deep sense of remorse and embarrassment at the thought of infecting others. It weighed heavily on my mind."

"Unfortunately, some people treated me brutally and retaliated against me once they found out about my COVID-19 diagnosis. It was a really tough experience."

Table 3. *The deeper look at the COVID-19 symptoms*

Theme	Codes	Result
Deeper look at the COVID-19 symptoms	Management of COVID-19 symptoms.	The majority of participants in the study (80%) managed their COVID-19 symptoms at home and/or in isolation. One participant required hospitalization, while another received outpatient care through online medical consultation and home-based care. These findings align with the current literature, which estimates that around 80% of COVID-19 cases are mild to moderate in severity, with only a small percentage being severe.
	Identified COVID-19 symptoms of the patient.	Participants were asked to identify all the symptoms they experienced during their illness with COVID-19. The study population (N=10) reported several well-recognized COVID-19 symptoms. The most commonly reported symptoms were fatigue (100%), shortness of breath (50%), decreased sense of smell or taste (60%), and fever (100%). These symptoms have also been identified in earlier studies, although the percentages of occurrence may vary across different populations.
	Perceptions, experiences and emotions of COVID-19 survivors.	The research also explored how the participants' mental health was affected while they were recovering from COVID-19. The recorded experiences showed that most participants had negative experiences with their mental health, while only a small number had positive experiences. Some participants expressed feelings of remorse and embarrassment for potentially infecting others they had encountered. There were instances where individuals experienced retaliation and mistreatment from their immediate environment after their condition became known.

Road to Recovery

Infected individuals with COVID-19 face a long and uncertain road to recovery, the specifics of which are mostly unknown. According to a statement by the Director-General of the World Health Organization (WHO) in February 2020, the amount of time needed to recover from moderate disease is two weeks, while the amount of time required to recover from severe or critical illness is between three and six weeks. However, the findings of our study suggest that seven out of ten participants, or seventy percent, had a recovery time greater than two weeks. More specifically, we discovered that the average amount of time it took for two participants to recover from the "majority of symptoms" was four weeks; the average amount of time it took for three non-hospitalized patients (i.e., patients with mild-to-moderate disease severity) was two weeks, whereas the average amount of time it took for two other patients (i.e., patients who had a more harrowing experience with COVID-19) was five weeks. While two of the patients who were hospitalized stated that the bulk of their symptoms were still present when they took part in the study, the length of their illness at the time that they took part in the survey was used as a proxy for the severity of their disease (i.e., date of participation minus date of symptom onset). This research also shows that COVID-19 survivors experienced significant variability in how long it took them to recover from the illness. This ranged from 0 days for asymptomatic patients to 18 weeks for a 55-year-old female participant with one preexisting condition and two

hospital visits for COVID-19-related symptoms.

In addition to the prolonged recovery durations discovered in this study, we found that four out of ten people, or forty percent, continued to exhibit symptoms of COVID-19 even after an average of sixty-five days had passed since the beginning of their illness. Figure 3B illustrates a list of such lingering symptoms and changes to general health that participants in this study identified. The most common problem identified was fatigue, which was reported by seven out of ten participants (70%); this was followed by shortness of breath, which was written by six participants (60%); and chest pain or distress, which was reported by five participants (50%).

More than half of the participants (seven out of ten, or 70%) stated that they had been subjected to stigma because of their COVID-19 infection, while the others (three out of ten, or 30%) said the opposite. Six recurring themes emerged from the additional accounts of the stigmas under which people who contracted COVID-19 were subjected. Avoidance by others after recovery was the type of stigma that occurred the most frequently (6/10, 60%), followed by others undermining the illness or experience of having COVID-19 (4/10, 40%). Other forms of discrimination include hostility and dismissal from members of the community who are at risk (3/10, 30%) and being blamed for contracting and spreading the virus (3/10, 30%). Also, there is discrimination at places of work and living (2/10, 20%). Lastly, shame and name-calling (2/10, 20%).

The study also found some positive experiences among a few of the survivors. One of the participants particularly expressed her journey to recovery that enabled her to learn new things, such as reading books and cooking meals; some reported their relatives and associates that made them feel loved and were encouraged not to get overwhelmed by the illness; a few said their process of recovery helped them have a better look at life in general rather than feel down for themselves over life after rehab.

Major Mentions

"I'm slowly improving, but it's been challenging. Some days are tougher than others, but I'm staying positive and taking it one step at a time."

"I'm doing well now. My symptoms have subsided, and I'm feeling much stronger. It's a relief to see progress and know I'm on the road to full recovery."

"Honestly, it's been tough. The fatigue and shortness of breath are still lingering, and it's frustrating. But I'm staying hopeful and focusing on caring for myself until I fully bounce back."

"I've established a new routine centered around safety. I wear masks in public, wash my hands thoroughly, and limit physical contact with others. I also make sure to follow the recommended guidelines for social interactions."

"It's been a mix of emotions. On the one hand, I'm relieved to be out of quarantine, but on the other hand, I'm still cautious about potential risks. I'm finding a balance between living my life and staying safe."

"Recovery has been a rollercoaster. Some days, I feel great, while on others, I experience setbacks. But overall, I'm grateful for my progress and remain determined to regain my health."

Minor Mentions

"I'm taking it one step at a time. There's still a lingering worry, but I'm gradually gaining confidence. I've started going back to work and engaging in social activities while following safety guidelines."

"It's been a bit overwhelming at times. After spending so much time in isolation, being around people again feels strange. But I'm taking baby steps and returning to normalcy."

"I'm adjusting surprisingly well. I've learned to appreciate the little things and not take my health and freedom for granted. I enjoy reconnecting with loved ones and slowly resuming my daily routines."

"I've become very cautious. I wear masks, maintain social distancing, and practice good hygiene. I've also educated myself about the importance of ventilation and regularly sanitizing high-touch surfaces."

"It's been a slow process, but I'm grateful for the small victories. I still have some symptoms, but I'm staying patient and trusting that I'll fully recover soon."

Table 4. *Road to recovery of COVID-19 patients*

<i>Theme</i>	<i>Codes</i>	<i>Result</i>
		The study found that the recovery time for COVID-19 varied among participants. While the World Health Organization (WHO) suggested a recovery time of two weeks for moderate disease and three to six weeks for severe or critical disease, the findings of this study indicated that seventy percent of participants had a recovery time greater than two weeks. The average recovery time for two participants who had recovered from the majority of symptoms was four weeks. Three non-

Road to Recovery	Length of time needed to recover from the virus	hospitalized patients with mild-to-moderate disease severity had an average recovery time of two weeks, while two other patients who had a more severe experience with COVID-19 took an average of five weeks to recover. Hospitalized patients still had significant symptoms at the time of the study, and their length of illness was used as a proxy for the severity of their illness.
	Lingering symptoms and changes to general health of the survivor	Forty percent of participants in the study continued to exhibit symptoms of COVID-19 even after an average of sixty-five days since the onset of their illness. The most common lingering symptoms reported by participants were fatigue (70%), shortness of breath (60%), and chest pain or distress (50%). These findings highlight the potential for long-term effects and the need for continued monitoring and support for COVID-19 survivors.
	Avoidance by others after recovery of symptoms	More than half of the participants (70%) reported experiencing stigma due to their COVID-19 infection. The most common type of stigma reported was avoidance by others after recovery (60%). This suggests that individuals who have recovered from COVID-19 may face social isolation and exclusion from their communities.
	People undermining the illness or experience with COVID-19	A significant portion of participants (40%) reported that others undermined their illness or experience with COVID-19. This could manifest as downplaying the severity of the illness or dismissing the challenges faced by COVID-19 survivors. Such attitudes can contribute to a lack of understanding and support for those recovering from the virus.
	Hostility and dismissal by those who are at risk	Some participants (30%) experienced hostility and dismissal from members of the community who are at risk. This may be due to fear and misunderstanding surrounding COVID-19 transmission, leading to negative attitudes and behaviors towards those who have contracted the virus.
	Blame for contracting and spreading the virus	Blaming COVID-19 survivors for contracting and spreading the virus was reported by a portion of participants (30%). Such blame can further stigmatize individuals and create a hostile environment for their recovery and reintegration into society.
	Discrimination at the place of work and living	A minority of participants (20%) reported discrimination at their places of work and living. This could involve unfair treatment, isolation, or negative reactions from colleagues, neighbors or other community members due to their COVID-19 infections.
	Shame and name – calling	Some participants (20%) experienced feelings of shame and encountered name-calling due to their COVID-19 infection. Such experiences can have a significant impact on the emotional well-being and mental health of individuals recovering from the virus.

Lessons Learned of COVID-19 Survivors

The survivors of COVID-19 are a valuable resource that is not being exploited to its full potential as a source of information. By participating in the surveys administered as part of this research, the individuals who had survived the pandemic could provide insights that, in their opinion, will assist society in better coping with the realities of the ongoing epidemic.

However, considering the recent spike in COVID-19 cases across the country, these findings are crucial for the public to understand because they are directed toward a larger population that the coronavirus may not have yet infected.

The following is a collection of essential takeaways from speaking with these COVID-19 survivors (along with a few actual quotations from participants):

"Any symptoms can be the virus. Thus, self-isolating is crucial even if you have a tickling in your throat. In the early stages of a mild case of COVID-19, it is simple to confuse the symptoms with those of a cold or allergies."

"Acknowledge the "truth that doctors and nurses do not have all the answers," and adjust your expectations per this realization."

"Traveling with COVID-19 can be nerve-racking and isolating, in addition to taxing the body, the mind, and the emotions. "At every turn, you are the one who is responsible for advocating for yourself."

"People who are young, healthy, and with no preexisting medical concerns may have a difficult time with COVID-19. "Take this matter very seriously. Guard both yourself and those around you."

"The disease symptoms manifest uniquely in each patient. There are many models that work for everyone. As a result of COVID-19, some people only have mild symptoms for a short period, while others struggle with chronic health problems."

"If you get the virus, you should treat it like a marathon, not a sprint. It is crucial to have patience throughout the rehabilitation process because it might be drawn out and unpredictable. The Onset of symptoms, as well as the continuation of symptoms, might occur in waves."

"If you need medical attention, do not put off going to the hospital for too long; research shows that waiting can result in poorer outcomes. In addition, there have been cases in which people have gone to the hospital but were sent home early or dismissed from their stay. Put your faith in your gut instinct because you are the only person with firsthand experience with your sickness."

"The existence of stigma during and after COVID-19 is a fact of life. Persons infected with the virus may elicit various responses from others, particularly in the early stages of their readjustment to everyday life. Some people may be heartless and callous in their acts and words."

The pandemic completely disrupted my goals. I had plans for career advancement and personal achievements, but everything stopped. It made me reevaluate my priorities and focus on staying healthy and supporting my loved ones

The pandemic taught me the importance of resilience and adaptability. It showed me the strength of human connection, even in times of physical distance. I also learned to appreciate the little things in life and not take them for granted.

Despite the hardships, there were some positive aspects. The pandemic allowed me to slow down and reevaluate my priorities. I spent more time with my family, pursued new hobbies, and developed a stronger sense of gratitude. It also made me realize the strength of our communities and the kindness of strangers.

The pandemic made me reassess what truly matters in life. It shifted my focus toward health, relationships, and personal well-being. It made me prioritize self-care and cherish the moments spent with loved ones. I now strive for a more balanced and fulfilling life.

Table 5. *The insights from Covid-19 survivors*

Theme	Code	Result
Insights from COVID-19 survivors	Realizations and takeaways of COVID 19 survivors	<p>The survivors of COVID-19 who participated in the surveys conducted as part of this research provided valuable insights and realizations that can assist society in better coping with the ongoing pandemic. These individuals, having experienced the challenges and consequences of the virus firsthand, offered unique perspectives on their journey to recovery and the impact of the pandemic on their lives.</p> <p>Their participation in the surveys allowed them to share their experiences and provide valuable information that can help the public gain a better understanding of the realities of COVID-19. These insights are particularly crucial considering the recent spike in COVID-19 cases across the country, as they are directed toward a larger population that the virus may not have yet infected.</p> <p>By harnessing the knowledge and experiences of COVID-19 survivors, society can benefit from their firsthand accounts, enabling better preparedness, prevention, and support systems for those affected by the virus. The information shared by survivors can contribute to the development of effective strategies, policies, and public health measures to mitigate the impact of COVID-19 and ensure the well-being of individuals and communities.</p>

Table 6. *The thematic analysis of themes with codes and sub themes*

Thematic Analysis of Themes		
Codes	Categories/Sub themes	Themes
1. People Infected with COVID-19.	Onset of symptoms	Onset, Testing and Contraction of COVID-19
2. COVID 19 symptoms experienced.		
3.Preventive/Precautionary measures to stop COVID- 19 contraction.	Knowledge on transmission of COVID	
4. Settings and workplaces of virus transmission.	Prevalent sources of virus transmission.	Deeper look at the COVID-19 symptoms
5. Management of COVID-19 symptoms.	Type of care	
6. Identified COVID-19 symptoms of the patient.	Prevalence of well recognized COVID - 19 survivors	
7. Perceptions, experiences and emotions of COVID-19 survivors.	Mental Health view of COVID 19 survivors	
8. Length of time needed to recover from the virus.	Recovery period of COVID 19 virus	Road to recovery
9. Lingering symptoms and changes to general health of the survivor	Prevalence of well recognized COVID - 19 symptoms reported.	

10. Avoidance by others after recovery of symptoms		
11. People undermining the illness or experience with COVID- 19		
12. Hostility and dismissal by those who are at risk	Social Stigma and discrimination	
13. Blame for contracting and spreading the virus		
14. Dissemination at the place of work and living		
15. Shame and name- calling		
16.Realizations and takeaways of COVID 19 survivors	Lessons learned from COVID 19 experiences	Insights from COVID-19 survivors

Intervention Program that promotes comprehensive recovery

Health And Wellness Recovery Program

It is an intervention program that promotes comprehensive recovery. The objective of a health and wellness program for COVID-19 survivors is to support their physical, mental, and emotional recovery following the illness. The program addressed the specific needs and challenges faced by survivors and assist them in regaining their health, improving their overall well-being, and reintegrating into daily life.

<i>Symptoms and challenges faced by COVID-19 Survivors</i>	<i>Inpatient intervention</i>	<i>Outpatient interventions</i>
Sudden disability with unexpected medical comorbidities	Validation and normalization of emotional responses. Exploring patient strengths and how they can be applied to achieve rehabilitation goals.	Validation and normalization of emotional responses. Sharing novel research findings. Reinforcing skills and abilities that are present and can be capitalized on.
Unfamiliarity with psychiatric symptoms and behavioral health care	Neuropsychology assessment/treatment is embedded and part of rehabilitation. De-emphasis on “psychopathology.” Framing of individual/group sessions as wellness and brain health.	Ongoing psychoeducation regarding prolonged stress response and normalizing evolving emotional responses.
Prolonged isolation	Group sessions with neuropsychologist. Social groups on unit. Internet- connected tablets to facilitate contact with family.	COVID-19 survivors support group. Behavioral activation facilitated by virtual visits with family. Virtual religious services. Live-streamed video games with friends.
Physiologic anxiety/panic in the setting of reduced oxygen capacity and dyspnea	Psychoeducation on avoidance in maintaining anxiety and habituation. Pretreatment psychological intervention. Co-treatment with PT/OT/SLP. Diaphragmatic breathing and Five finger breathing. Guided imagery.	Ongoing psychoeducation regarding somatic anxiety/ panic unlikely to be dangerous or life-threatening. Consult with outpatient rehabilitation team: If breathing exercises are not contraindicated, attempt exposure to breathing exercises, body scan, and deep breathing exercises.
Uncertainty regarding disease course, functional outcome, and reinfection	Mindfulness exercises to promote present-moment awareness. Cognitive restructuring. Reflection on progress made to date. Focus on short-term rehabilitation goals.	Psychoeducation. Reduction of reassurance-seeking behaviors (i.e., checking pulse oximeter excessively) and exposure/habituation to uncertainty. Experiential and guided mindfulness exercises to promote perspective taking and radical acceptance. Cognitive restructuring. Reflect on concrete examples of progress over the course of rehabilitation
Fear and avoidance of rehabilitation and medical care	Psychoeducation on avoidance in maintaining anxiety and habituation. Pretreatment psychological intervention. Co-treatment with PT/OT/SLP. Guided imagery of goal attainment	Psychoeducation on counter productiveness of experiential avoidance. Gradual exposure. Discussion of communication skills to effectively communicate with medical providers.
Health literary	Psychoeducation	Psychoeducation and discussion of use and potential implications of homeopathic remedies traditionally used in patient culture.

Community stigma	Help patients to anticipate and problem solve social interactions after discharge.	Psychoeducation on misconceptions of COVID-19, psychiatric conditions, and prognosis. Provide informational resources to follow-up with social services, food banks in the local area, and programs that can help subsidize living and health care expenses.
Economic uncertainty and financial distress	Normalize and validate uncertainty and coordinate with unit social workers for outpatient services.	Assistance with additional problem solving, such as generating support from family/friends.

Conclusions

The findings presented in this study are tentative and come from a small cohort of COVID-19 survivors. It is common knowledge that many people recover from COVID-19; nonetheless, the findings of this study indicate that the road to recovery may be slow and difficult for specific individuals. To provide an accurate depiction of the journey with COVID-19, it is essential to be aware that the recovery time can be more than two weeks for patients who are only experiencing minor symptoms. In addition, a sizeable percentage of those who made it through COVID-19 are termed "long haulers." People who continue to suffer symptoms weeks or even months after their first infection with the virus are considered to have persistent symptoms.

Additional research is required to fully understand the factors contributing to the wide range of responses to the new coronavirus. In addition to this, thousands of individuals have passed away because of infection with the same virus, with an abnormally high rate of fatalities occurring among residents of Tarlac City. Therefore, additional research is required to gain a better understanding of the circumstances surrounding cases that resulted in fatalities and to assist in preventing a similar outcome for others.

The findings of this study indicate that for certain individuals, the road to recovery for self-care patients in isolation is slow and challenging. While a result, it is advised that a policy be established for the creation of an intervention program that supports and encourages comprehensive recovery and will care for the patients' physical and psychological well-being as they move through the self-care phase of their recovery.

A self-care intervention program must be supported with high-quality, evidence-based tools. These include prescription drugs, counseling, diagnostics, and/or digital technologies that can be used completely or in part outside of established medical setting.

The data gathered indicates that there is a pressing need to enhance health, especially in the areas of exercise, diet, rest, safety, and quality of life. Self-care intervention program is an intentional activity that consists of self-care plan through reflection and assessment that provides for the physical, psychological, and spiritual well-being. It uses a Stress Management Tool to reduce stress, refuels recovery capacity through remote counseling and consultation, encourages safety and better care, and enhances quality of life.

As a final recommendation, the Self-care Intervention Program should be made a requirement through policy or integrated into the code of ethics in every company or institution. The Self-care Intervention Program's clause must say that everyone has a moral obligation to protect the welfare of others as well as their own well-being, and that this obligation extends to themselves as well. These obligations include upholding moral and ethical integrity, promoting health and safety, maintaining competence, and continuing professional and personal development.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Danica V. Delima

UP Manila School of Health Sciences – Philippines